

Elastico-viscous Fluid Flow between Two Parallel Plates Under The Assumption of No-slip on The Solid Boundary

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Abstract

The study of inelastico-viscous flow between two parallel plates, under the assumption of a no-slip boundary condition, focuses on examining the motion of a fluid governed simultaneously by viscous and elastic forces, with the fluid firmly adhering to the plate surfaces. This type of flow problem is particularly relevant for understanding the dynamics of viscoelastic fluids when confined within narrow geometries. Such investigations provide valuable insights into the mechanical response of complex fluids and have significant applications in engineering and technology, including lubrication systems, polymer processing, biomedical fluid mechanics, and microfluidic device design.

Keywords

Viscous Laminar Flow, Two Parallel Plates, Visco-elastic Fluid, Incompressible Fluid.

Introduction

The problem of viscous laminar flow between two parallel plates is of considerable interest because it closely approximates flows frequently encountered in engineering and technological applications. An additional advantage is that the governing equations of motion become highly simplified, permitting exact analytical solutions.

Unsteady motion of Newtonian fluids between concentric rotating cylinders has been investigated by several researchers. Ramacharyulu (1979) studied the laminar flow of a viscous liquid between two parallel plates, while Murthy (1986) extended the analysis to second-order viscoelastic fluids confined between porous parallel plates. It was observed that the inclusion of an elastico-viscosity parameter raises the order of the governing differential equation from two to three, requiring natural permeable boundary conditions for solution. To make the problem physically meaningful, a third boundary condition was introduced by considering the influence of the bounding surfaces.

Objective of study

In this paper related work, Jat and Jhankal (2003) examined three-dimensional free-convective magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) flow and heat transfer of a viscous incompressible fluid through a porous medium bounded by a vertical infinite porous plate. Their results highlighted the significant roles of the magnetic field and permeability parameters on flow and heat transfer characteristics. Sharma and Biradar (2004) analyzed the radial inflow and outflow of a second-order fluid beneath an enclosed rotating disc, extending solutions from small Reynolds numbers to larger values. Despite differences in geometry, these investigations generally did not address the influence of elastico-viscosity on flow variables. Moreover, the field variables were typically analyzed using classical analytical methods or finite difference approximations.

Review of Literature

The present work aims to address the general problem of unsteady flow between two infinitely long parallel plates, under the standard no-slip condition at solid boundaries. While this problem has been studied extensively for more than a decade, the approaches of Ramacharyulu (1964) and Ramacharyulu et al. (1979) are particularly noteworthy. Unlike classical approaches, however, the present analysis applies Duhamel's theorem as a novel tool to evaluate flow variables. The unsteady-state problem is categorized into three physical cases, each associated with distinct boundary conditions: (i) prescribed fluid velocity at both boundaries, (ii) fluid velocity specified at one boundary and shear stress at the other, and (iii) shear stress prescribed at both boundaries as functions of time. It is observed that the first two classes of problems are well-posed and yield valid solutions, whereas the third case, involving specification of velocity gradients at both boundaries, conflicts with momentum conservation. As a result, this final formulation is not properly defined, and no solution can be obtained.

These three classes of boundary conditions, when expressed mathematically, are found to be special cases of one more general set of boundary conditions. Each of the original

sets corresponds to a particular choice for the constants appearing in the more general set.

Analysis

Formulation of the problem

A set of rectangular cartesian co-ordinates (X,Y,Z), with axis-X along one of the two plates, is considered. Further, the Y axis is perpendicular to the plane of the plates; the plates being Y = 0 and Y = L. The two plates are assumed to be infinite so that all the physical quantities are independent of X. Now the velocity components characterizing the rectilinear flow between the plates are given by (U(Y,T),0,0) in the X, Y and Z directions. The equation of the motion in X – direction is given by:

$$\rho \frac{\partial U}{\partial T} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial X} + \frac{\phi_1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} + \phi_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} \right)$$

The equation of motion in Y – direction is given by

$$0 = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial Y} + (2\phi_2 + \phi_3) \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial Y} \right)^2$$

The initial condition is

$$U(Y,0) = F(Y)$$

and the boundary conditions are:

$$\alpha_1 U(0,T) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} [U(0,T)] = \psi_1(T), \quad T \geq 0$$

$$\alpha_3 U(1,T) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} [U(1,T)] = \psi_2(T), \quad T \geq 0$$

Let us introduce the non-dimensional parameters as:

$$U_i = \frac{\phi_1 u_i}{\rho L}, \quad T = \frac{\rho L^2 t}{\phi_1}, \quad \phi_2 = \rho L^2 \beta, \quad P = \frac{\phi_1^2 p}{\rho L^2}$$

$$X_i = Lx_i, \quad Y_i = Ly_i, \quad \phi_3 = \rho L^2 \nu_c, \quad A_i = \frac{\phi_1^2 u_i}{\rho^2 L^3}$$

$$S_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\phi_1^2 s_{\frac{1}{2}}}{\rho L^2}, \quad E_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(1)} = \frac{\phi_1^2 e_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(1)}}{\rho L^2}, \quad E_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(2)} = \frac{\phi_1^2 e_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(2)}}{\rho^2 L^4}$$

The equation of motion in x – direction in the non-dimensional form is:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

while the equation of motion in y – direction is:

$$0 = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + (2\beta + v_c) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2$$

with the initial condition:

$$u(y, 0) = f(y)$$

together with the boundary conditions:

$$\alpha_1 u(0, t) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [u(0, t)] = \psi_1(t), \quad t \geq 0$$

$$\alpha_3 u(1, t) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [u(1, t)] = \psi_2(t), \quad t \geq 0$$

where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ and α_4 are constants and $\psi_1(t) = 1, \psi_2(t) = 0$ are prescribed functions of the time-parameter (t) while f(y) is a prescribed function of y. So as to maintain the generality of the problem, it is assumed that the pressure gradient $-\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \alpha(t)$.

Solution of the problem

The boundary value problem formulated above involves a non-homogeneous differential Equation (2.6) with two varying boundary conditions and a non-zero initial condition. The linearity of the governing Equation (2.6), the initial and the boundary conditions allow us a linear transformation of the type:

$$u(y, t) = u_1(y, t) + u_2(y, t) + u_3(y, t) + u_4(y, t)$$

Where the functions $u_1(y, t)$ and $u_2(y, t)$ are associated with respective line varying boundary conditions on $y = 0$ and $y = 1$; the function $u_3(y, t)$ with the viscous decay of the initial velocity distribution with the exclusion of the pressure term in the Equation (2.1). The function $u_4(y, t)$ is associated with the sudden application and subsequent

maintenance of pressure gradient $\alpha(t)$. So, the functions $u_1(y, t), u_2(y, t), u_3(y, t)$ and $u_4(y, t)$ are to be determined to find the solution of the problem.

Determination of $u_1(y, t)$ and $u_2(y, t)$

The auxiliary problem which determines $F_1(y, t)$ is :

$$\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 F_1}{\partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F_1}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

$$F_1(y, 0) = 0;$$

with the initial condition:

together with the boundary conditions:

$$\alpha_1 F_1(0, t) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_1(0, t)] = 1$$

$$\alpha_3 F_1(1, t) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_1(1, t)] = 0$$

$$F_1(y, t) = F_s(y) + F_u(y, t)$$

Letting

where $F_s(y), F_u(y, t)$ are steady and unsteady state solutions, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial^2 F_s}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad \text{at } t=0$$

subject to:

$$\alpha_1 F_s(0) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_s(0)] = 1$$

$$\alpha_3 F_s(1) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_s(1)] = 0$$

for which steady state solution is

$$F_1(y) = A_1 y + B_1$$

where

$$A_1 = \frac{(1 + \alpha_1(\alpha_3 + \alpha_4))}{\alpha_2(\alpha_2\alpha_3 - \alpha_3\alpha_4 - \alpha_4\alpha_1)}$$

and

$$B_1 = -\frac{(\alpha_3 + \alpha_4)}{(\alpha_2\alpha_3 - \alpha_3\alpha_4 - \alpha_4\alpha_1)}$$

The unsteady state motion is governed by:

$$\frac{\partial F_u}{\partial t} = \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F_u}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

together with conditions

$$\alpha_1 F_u(0,t) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_u(0,t)] = 0$$

$$\alpha_3 F_u(1,t) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_u(1,t)] = 0$$

$$F_1(y) = -F_u(y,0)$$

Assuming $F_u = e^{-\frac{a_1^2 t}{\beta}}$ [A Cosy + B Siny] as a trial solution, we obtain from Equation (2.11)

$$F_u(y,t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} C_j p_j(y) e^{-\frac{a_1^2 t}{\beta}}$$

where the Eigen functions are given by

$$p_j(y) = \alpha_2 \lambda_j \cos \lambda_j y - \alpha_1 \sin \lambda_j y$$

and the Eigen values λ_j are the roots of

$$\tan \lambda = \lambda \frac{(\alpha_2\alpha_3 - \alpha_1\alpha_4)}{(\alpha_1\alpha_3 + \alpha_2\alpha_4\lambda^2)}$$

It is noticed that the sequence $[p_j(y)]$ is orthogonal in [0,1] within the norm

$$\|p_j(y)\|^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 \lambda_j^2) + \frac{(\alpha_1\alpha_3 - \alpha_2\alpha_4)(\alpha_1\alpha_4 - \alpha_2\alpha_3)}{(\alpha_3^2 + \alpha_4^2 \lambda_j^2)} \right]$$

The constant C_j are determined from the initial condition of equation

$$-F_u(y,t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} C_j p_j(y)$$

Which yields

$$C_j = \frac{1}{\lambda_j \|p_j(y)\|^2}$$

Hence,

$$F_1(y,t) = F_1(y) + F_u(y,t)$$

$$F_1(y,t) = A_1 y + B_1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} C_j p_j(y) e^{-\frac{a_1^2 t}{\beta}}$$

Employing Duhamel's Theorem

$$u_1(y,t) = \int_0^t \psi_1(\tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [F_1(y,t-\tau)] d\tau$$

$$u_1(y,t) = -\frac{1}{1+\beta} \sum_{j=1}^n C_j p_j e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}} \int_0^t \psi_1(\tau) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 \tau}{1+\beta}} d\tau$$

Proceeding for $u_2(y,t)$ in the same lines as that for $u_1(y,t)$, we obtain

$$u_2(y,t) = -\frac{1}{1+\beta} \sum_{j=1}^n C_j p_j e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}} \int_0^t \psi_2(\tau) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 \tau}{1+\beta}} d\tau$$

Where

$$D_j = \frac{\sqrt{(\alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2)} \sqrt{(\alpha_3^2 + \alpha_4^2)}}{\|p_j(y)\|^2}$$

Determination of $u_3(y,t)$

It can be seen that $u_3(y,t)$ can be expressed as

$$u_3(y,t) = \sum_{j=1}^n E_j p_j(y) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}}$$

Where the constants E_j can be obtained by using initial condition.

$$E_j = \frac{\int_0^1 f(y) p_j(y) dy}{\|p_j(y)\|^2}$$

Determination of $u_4(y,t)$

From Equation 2.6

$$\frac{\partial F_4}{\partial \alpha} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{\partial^2 F_4}{\partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F_4}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

$$F_4(y,t) = F_s(y) + F_u(y,t)$$

and letting the solution as:

where $F_s(y)$ and $F_u(y,t)$ are steady and unsteady state solutions, the boundary and initial conditions will become

$$\alpha_1 F_s(0) + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_s(0)] = 1$$

$$\alpha_3 F_s(1) + \alpha_4 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [F_s(1)] = 0$$

and

$$F_s(y) = -F_u(y,0)$$

for which the steady state solution is

$$F_s(y) = -\frac{1}{1+\beta} \left[\frac{y^2}{2} + A_1 y + B_1 \right]$$

where,

$$A_1 = \frac{2\alpha_3 - \alpha_1 \alpha_3 - 2\alpha_4 \alpha_1}{2\alpha_1 \alpha_3 + 2\alpha_1 - 2\alpha_3 \alpha_2}$$

and

$$B_1 = \frac{1 + \alpha_2 (2\alpha_3 - \alpha_1 \alpha_2 - 2\alpha_4 \alpha_1)}{-\alpha_1}$$

The unsteady state solution is given by:

$$F_u(y,t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} F_j p_j(y) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}}$$

where F_j are obtained from the initial conditions as:

$$F_j = - \frac{\int_0^1 f(y) u_4(y,0) p_j(y) dy}{\|p_j(y)\|^2}$$

Hence,

$$u_4(y,t) = - \left(\frac{y^2}{2} + A_1 y + B_1 \right) + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} F_j p_j(y) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}}$$

Where A_1 and B_1 are given in Equations (3.34) and (3.35) respectively.

Employing Duhamel's Theorem, we obtain

$$u_4(y,t) = - \frac{1}{1+\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (\alpha_1 C_j + \alpha_2 D_j) p_j(y) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}} \int_0^t \Phi(\tau) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 \tau}{1+\beta}} d\tau$$

Therefore, the solution of the velocity field satisfying the conditions [Equation (2.9), Equation (2.10) and Equation (2.11) are given by:

$$u(y,t) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} p_j(y) e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 t}{1+\beta}} \left[E_j - \int_0^t \frac{1}{1+\beta} \lambda_j^2 \left[C_j \psi_1(\tau) + D_j \psi_2(\tau) \right] + (\alpha_1 C_j + \alpha_2 D_j) \Phi(\tau) \right] e^{-\frac{\alpha_j^2 \tau}{1+\beta}} d\tau$$

Skin-friction on lower and upper plates are given by $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$ at $y = 0$ and $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$ at $y = 1$ respectively.

Conclusion

The velocity profiles for various values of t and β are presented graphically in Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2. It is observed that as the elasto-viscosity parameter β increases, the velocity profiles are found to be more steep and further, as t increase, the velocity profiles are significantly distributed. The skin friction on lower and upper plates for different values of elasto-viscosity parameter β and t are presented graphically in Figure 2.3. It is observed that as t increases, the skin friction on the plates also increases. Further, as the elasto-viscosity parameter $\beta \rightarrow 0$, the result coincides with of a Newtonian fluid discussed by Ramacharyulu *et al.* (1979).

From this study, it is found that as the elasto-viscosity of the fluid increases (while retaining all the other material properties as constants), the velocity profiles are more parabolic in nature. Due to the sudden application of pressure gradient, the intra-molecular forces tend to pull the neighbouring cluster of fluid elements. As a result of this, the fluid velocity at bottom plate is high and reduces. At a shorter duration (i.e. as time-parameter (t) reduces), the velocity profiles are found to be more parabolic. This is due to the fact that immediately after the application of the pressure gradient, the velocity of the fluid near the bounding surfaces is high and as time passes, the intra-molecular forces reduces which is in accordance with the physical observable phenomena. It is also found that for a constant elasto-viscosity of the fluid, the profiles become more steep with an increase of time. □

Figure Captions

- 2.1 Velocity versus plates separation for $t = 0.3$
- 2.2 Velocity versus plates separation for $t = 0.2$
- 2.3 Skin friction versus elasto-viscosity parameter

Figure 2.1: Velocity versus stream function for $\beta=0.4$.

Figure 2.2: Velocity versus stream function for $\beta=0.2$.

Figure 2.3: Skin friction versus stream function for $\beta=0.4$.

Figure 2.4: Skin friction versus stream function for $\beta=0.2$.

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